

Studies on photodegradation of Tropaeolin O (Acid Orange 6) in aqueous solution using immobilized Dowex-11 photocatalyst

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Abstract : The present study involves the photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O (Acid Orange 6), employing heterogeneous photocatalytic process. Photocatalytic activity of immobilized Dowex-11 photocatalyst has been investigated. An attempt has been made to study the effect of process parameters viz. amount of catalyst, concentration of dye, light intensity and pH on photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O. The experiments were carried out by irradiating the aqueous solutions of dyes containing photocatalyst with UV-light. The rate of degradation was estimated from residual concentration spectrophotometrically. Similar experiments were carried out by varying pH (3.5–11.5), amount of catalyst (1–3 g), initial concentration of dye (10 to 70 mg L⁻¹) and light intensity (5.2–15.6 mW cm⁻²). The dye is decolorized in 80 min and completely degraded in 180 min under optimum conditions. Removal efficiency results (98%) after 3 h. Kinetic analysis of photodegradation reveals that the degradation follows approximately pseudo-first order kinetics according to the Langmuir-Hinshelwood model. Carbon dioxide, nitrate and sulphate ions have been identified as mineralization products.

Keywords : Photocatalysis, Tropaeolin O, kinetic analysis, UV-light, photocatalytic degradation, azo dye.

Introduction

Textile industries produce large volume of colored dye effluents which are toxic and non-biodegradable. Azo dye Tropaeolin O creates severe environmental problems by releasing toxic and potential carcinogenic substances into the aqueous phase. Various chemical and physical processes such as precipitation, adsorption, air stripping, flocculation, reverse osmosis and ultra filtration can be used for color removal from textile effluents¹⁻³. However these techniques are non-destructive, since they only transfer the non-biodegradable matter into sludge, giving rise to new type of pollution, which needs further treatment^{4,5}. Recently there has been considerable interest in the utilization of advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) for the complete destruction of dyes. AOPs are based on generation of reactive species such as hydroxyl radicals that oxidizes a broad range of organic pollutants quickly and non-selectively^{6,7}. AOPs include photocatalysis systems such as combination of semiconductors and light, and semiconductor and oxidants. Heterogeneous photocatalysis has emerged as an important destructive technology leading to the total mineralization of most of the

organic pollutants including organic reactive dyes⁸⁻¹¹.

Ever since 1977, when Frank and Bard^{12,13} first examined the possibilities of using TiO₂ to decompose cyanide in water, there has been increasing interest in environmental applications. Some other newly developed photocatalyst are alkali and alkaline earth tantalates TiO₂ and other photocatalyst in different application with new techniques a new group of photocatalyst materials have arisen for splitting of water into H₂ and O₂ and organic molecular degradation under ultra-violet/visible light irradiation. Heller¹⁴ pointed out that, all the extensive knowledge that was gained during the development of semiconductor photoelectrochemistry during the 1970s and 1980s greatly assist the development of photocatalysis process. Many researchers agree that transition metal oxide such as TiO₂, ZnO₂, CdS and WO₃ etc. are excellent photocatalytically breaking down organic pollutants.

Bhatkhande *et al.*¹⁵ reviewed recent works in this area and listed the compounds degraded by photocatalysis by various research. In recently published research work on degradation of azo dyes of textile effluent and photocata-

lyst, Legrini *et al.*¹⁶ in 1993 suggested that the purification with TiO₂ photocatalyst in presence of UV radiation has been known to have several advantages such as effective removal of organic compounds dissolved or dispersed in water and inexpensive cost. Styliidi *et al.*¹⁷ proposed a TiO₂-mediated photodegradation mechanism for Acid Orange 7, what led to the complete mineralization of the organic molecule into naphthalene and benzene type rings and carbon into CO₂, nitrogen into NH₄⁺ and NO₃, sulphur into SO₄²⁻ ions. Chin Cheng Hsu and Wu carried out degradation of methyl orange under UV-light (300 nm) illumination using ZnO/ZnO₂ as photocatalyst¹⁸. Wang *et al.*¹⁹ reported enhanced photocatalytic activity for methyl orange degradation using SO₄²⁻/ZnO/TiO₂ and ZnO as photocatalysts respectively. Mendez-Pazet *et al.*²⁰ carried out anaerobic treatment of azo dyes Acid Orange 7 under Fed batch and continues condition. The removal rate of dye pollutant is increased at high rate when some glucose is added to reaction mixture. Degradation of Acid Green 16 was studied by Sakthivel *et al.*²¹ using ZnO irradiated with sunlight. Here the photodegradation efficiency decreased with an increase in initial dye concentration. Optimum catalyst loading was found to be 250 mg in 100 ml. Akyol *et al.*²² worked on photocatalytic degradation of dyes of different industries. Poulivos and Tsachpinis²³ investigated the photocatalytic degradation of Reactive Black 5, using different semi conducting oxides, TiO₂, UV-100 TiO₂, ZnO and TiO₂/WO₃. Four parallel black light blue fluorescent tubes were used as the UV-light source.

Experimental

We use Methylene Blue Immobilized Resin Dowex-11 for oxidative degradation of dye contaminants. Methylene Blue Immobilized Resin is a newly developed photocatalyst and has vast potential of degradation of azo dyes. Methylene Blue can be act as sensitizer for light induced process. Due to sensitization of photocatalyst, electron migrates from valance band (VB) to conduction band (CB) and holes are formed in valance band and these holes can generate hydroxyl radicals which are highly oxidizing in nature. Probably hole can react with dye molecule and abstract electron from dye molecule and process of degradation start. Lots of studies have been reported on the photocatalytic degradation of azo dyes. Photocatalyst

materials are so limited and available catalysts are not capable for complete mineralization of wastewater of textile industries so we require catalyst which can remove dye contaminate of textile industries.

Tropaeolin O (Acid Orange 6) :

IUPAC name = Sodium 4-[(2,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-diazenyl]benzenesulfonate

Molecular formula = C₁₂H₉N₂NaO₅S

Molecular weight = 316.27 g/mol

Appearance = Orange-yellow

Solubility in water = Partially soluble

λ_{\max} = 387 nm

Fig. 1. Structure of Tropaeolin O.

Effect of irradiation time :

The relationship between the percentage degradation and irradiation time is shown in Fig. 2. It is clearly seen that the percentage degradation increases with increasing irradiation time. The light induced degradation proceeds with a slow kinetics after one-hour irradiation (see Fig. 2). This indicates the formation of intermediates and its competitiveness with parent dye molecules in the photocatalytic degradation process.

Bandara *et al.*²⁴ have attributed the slow kinetics of dye degradation after certain time limit due to the difficulty in converting the N-atoms of dye into oxidised nitrogen compounds. This has been observed during photocatalytic degradation of C-N bonds in aliphatic compounds (Maillard *et al.*²⁵). Under the given experimental conditions the complete degradation has occurred within 180 min using immobilized Dowex-11 photocatalyst. The photocatalytic degradation of the dye occurs on the surface of catalyst where OH[•] and O₂[•] radicals are available for photocatalytic degradation. Hydroxyl radicals are formed from the holes in valance band reacting with either water OH⁻ adsorbed on the catalyst surface. The OH[•] radicals are

Fig. 2. Effect of irradiation time for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (catalyst loading : 2 g, pH : 7.5, solution volume : 200 ml and light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

strong enough to break the different bonds in the dye molecules (N=N, C-C, C=N, C-N, C-S and C=N) adsorbed on the surface of catalyst which lead to the formation of carbon dioxide and inorganic ions such as NH⁺, NO₃⁻, Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻. The formation of OH• radicals and O₂[•] increases with increase in irradiation time and hence the dye is completely degraded in the course of time.

Effect of initial dye concentration :

The pollutant concentration is a very important parameter in textile wastewater treatment. The effect of initial Tropaeolin O concentration on the degradation efficiency was studied by varying the concentration from 10 to 70 mg L⁻¹ and keeping photocatalyst (2 g/200 ml) as constant. The results are shown in Fig. 3. Increase in the dye concentration from 10 to 70 mg L⁻¹ decreases the percentage removal of Tropaeolin O from 85.26 to 79.41 % in 100 min of radiation time. The degradation efficiency of Tropaeolin O was found to decrease with an increase in the initial dye concentration (Fig. 3). The active surface on the catalyst available for reaction is very crucial

for the degradation to take place, but as the dye concentration is increased and the catalyst amount is kept constant, results in fewer active sites for the reaction^{26,27}. With increased dye molecules the solution became more intense coloured and the path length of photons entering the solution decreased thereby only fewer photons reached the catalyst surface. And therefore, the production of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals was limited. At still higher concentration of the dye, the path length was further reduced and the photodegradation was found to be negligible.

Effect of catalyst loading :

The amount of catalyst is one of the main parameter for the degradation studies. In order to determine the effect of catalyst loading, the experiments were performed by varying catalyst loading from 1 to 3 g for dye solutions of 40 mg/L at pH 7.4. The degradation efficiency for various catalysts loading for Tropaeolin O has been depicted in Fig. 4. Fig. 4 reveals that initial slopes of the curves increase greatly by increasing catalyst loading from 1 to 3 g for Tropaeolin O there after the rate of degrada-

Fig. 3. Effect of variation in dye concentration for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (catalyst loading : 2 g, pH : 7.5, solution volume : 200 ml and light intensity : 10.4 mW cm^{-2}).

Fig. 4. Effect of variation in catalyst loading for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, pH : 7.5, solution volume : 200 ml and light intensity : 10.4 mW cm^{-2}).

tion remains almost constant. The degradation efficiency increases with increase in the catalyst loading up to limit.

The photocatalytic destruction of other organic pollutants has also exhibited the same dependency on cata-

lyst dose²⁸. This can be explained on the basis that optimum catalyst loading is found to be dependent on initial solute concentration because with the increase of catalyst dosage, total active surface area increases, hence avail-

ability of more active sites on catalyst surface²⁹.

Effect of variation of light intensity :

The variation of light intensity is one of the main parameter for the degradation studies. In order to determine the effect of light intensity, the experiments were performed by varying light intensity from 5.2 to 15.6 mW cm⁻² for dye solutions of 40 mg/L at pH 7.4. The results obtained are reported in Fig. 5. The above shows that an increase in light intensity increases the rate of photocatalytic degradation^{30,31}. As the intensity of light

increases the degradation from 81 to 91% at the time of 150 min. Photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O increases with increase in pH up to a pH value of 7.5 and then decreases again with increase in pH value above 7.5. This behavior may be explained on the basis that the increase in the rate of photocatalytic degradation may be due to the increased availability of OH⁻ at higher pH values³²⁻³⁴. By combining with holes, OH⁻ ions will generate more hydroxyl radicals (OH[•]) which are considered responsible for the photocatalytic degradation. Above a pH value of 7.5, the increased number of OH⁻ ions will

Fig. 5. Effect of variation in light intensity for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, catalyst loading : 2 g, solution volume : 200 ml and pH : 7.5).

increases, the number of photons striking per unit area of the photocatalyst also increases. A linear behavior between light intensity and the rate of reaction was observed. Since light intensity increases more than 15.6 mW cm⁻² and increases the temperature of dye solution and a thermal reaction may occur, therefore higher intensities were avoided

Effect of pH variation :

The most important parameter that influences the photocatalytic degradation is the solution pH. The efficiency of the catalyst is affected by pH of the solution. The effect of pH on the photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O as a function of time is given in Fig. 6. Increase of pH of the dye solution from 3.5 to 7.5 in-

competes with the electron rich dye. The OH⁻ ions will make the surface of the semiconductor negatively charged and as a consequence of repulsive force between two negatively charged species (OH⁻ ions and the electron rich dye), the approach of Tropaeolin O molecules to the semiconductor surface will be retarded. This will result in a decrease in the rate of photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O dye.

Kinetic study :

The photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O was observed at $\lambda_{max} = 387$ nm. The optimum condition was obtained at initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, catalyst loading : 2 g, solution volume : 200 ml, light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻², pH : 7.5 and temperature = 308 K. The

Fig. 6. Effect of variation in pH for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, catalyst loading : 2 g, solution volume : 200 ml and light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

plot of $1 + \log \text{O.D.}$ versus exposure time is a straight line (Fig. 7), which indicates that the photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O follows pseudo-first order kinetics^{35,36}. The rate constant (k) for the reaction was determined using the expression. Rate = k [Tropaeolin

O], $K = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$. The rate constant for this reaction is $K = 1.56 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed data, the following tentative mechanism may be proposed for photocatalytic deg-

Fig. 7. Kinetic study for Tropaeolin O-photocatalyst system (initial dye concentration : 40 mg/L, pH : 7.5, catalyst loading : 2 g, solution volume : 200 ml and light intensity : 10.4 mW cm⁻²).

radation of Tropaeolin O. The possible mechanism of this process is as follows :

When the solution of the dye was exposed to light, in presence of photocatalyst, initially the Tropaeolin O molecules are excited to first excited singlet state (Tropaeolin O^{*1}). Then these excited molecules are transferred to the triplet state through inter system crossing (ISC). The triplet dye (Tropaeolin O^{*3}) may donate its electron to the photocatalyst and the dye becomes positively charged. The dissolved oxygen of the solution will pull an electron from the conduction band of the semiconductor thus regenerating the semiconductor.

The positively charged molecules of the dye (Tropaeolin O⁺) will immediately react with OH⁻ ions to form OH[•] radicals that will convert the dye molecules into products^{37,38}.

Conclusion :

Aim of the present work is to gain attention of researchers toward utilization of solar energy for degradation of dye pollutants by photocatalyst and find out new photocatalyst for different applications. The potential of degradation of (Tropaeolin O, is an azo dye used as model compound for experiment) dyes by (Methylene Immobilized Resin Dowex-11) catalyst is better and this catalyst works well in dim light also. We apply it in different condition and find out the effect of different parameters on rate of degradation.

As compared to solar photocatalytic systems with other catalyst, Methylene Blue Immobilized Resin Dowex-11 used as solar photocatalysts gives very good results and successfully improved the degradation rate of organic dyes. It believed that the improved color degradation capability is due to the fact that the visible region of the solar radia-

tion excites the Methylene Blue Immobilized Resin, followed by a series of photosensitizing reactions. The photocatalytic degradation of Tropaeolin O has been studied using Methylene Blue Immobilized Resin Dowex-11 as photocatalyst. The photocatalytic degradation of the dyes follows first order kinetics for the system.

The photocatalytic degradation efficiency has been generally, found to increase with increase in catalyst loading. The photocatalytic transformation decreases with increases in initial dye concentration. With the increase in the concentration of a dye solution, the number of photons decreases, to reach the catalyst surface, decreasing the number of photons absorbed by the catalyst and all the degradations occur at an optimal pH 7.5 value.

Therefore this technology has very good potential of organic molecular degradation from complex molecule into simpler molecules. Azo dyes which polluted water large part of textile effluent can transform into color less and non toxic compounds so this catalyst may applicable for industrial purpose for improvement in quality of the wastewater of textile industries and many others.

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